

Fig. 1. ○—Alkane; ○—Ether, Fluoro, Aldehyde; △—Iodo, Thiol, Ester; ○—Amine; ×—Nitrile; φ—Nitrate; ⊖—Nitro; ⊗—Chloro, Alcohol; ⊕—Bromo; □—Sulphide.

compound within these series becomes possible, provided the value of C for the particular series is known.

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Chemical Examination of the Bark of *Terminalia myriocarpa*-Heurek and Muell-Arg

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Manuscript received 23 October 1979, revised 8 September 1980,
accepted 13 April 1981

VARIOUS species of the genus *Terminalia* (family: Combretaceae) have been investigated by different workers¹⁻⁵ and have been shown to contain tomentonic, gallic, chebulic, chebulinic, arjunolic

acids, β -sitosterol, sapogenins and hydroxy stilbene glucoside etc. Literature survey indicated that no work has so far been reported on the chemical constituents of *Terminalia myriocarpa*. *Terminalia myriocarpa* is a very large evergreen woody tree, the bark of which is used as a potent cardiac stimulant and mild diuretic⁶⁻⁷. This paper reports the general phytochemical screening and the systematic examination of the bark of the plant.

The alcoholic extract of the bark was tested with Mayer and Dragendroff reagents, Libermann-Burchard reagent, Kedde reagent, Shinoda reagent and for froth formation. In all the tests, the responses were negative indicating the absence of alkaloids, steroids, triterpenoids, cardenolides, flavonoids and saponoides from the bark.

Experimental

The powdered bark (142 g) was refluxed with petrol (1/1) for 18 hrs. The extract on concentration gave a syrupy liquid which on column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1), yielded β -sitosterol confirmed by comparison with authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p. and co-tlc).

The defatted bark was then extracted with chloroform (800 ml) for 10 hrs. The concentrated extract (0.90 g) on trituration with petroleum ether gave an insoluble portion (0.06 g) which did not respond to triterpenoid and saponin tests and was found to be the same substance as that obtained in the methanolic extract by co-tlc, uv and ir comparisons.

The above bark residue was then extracted with methanol (1/1) for 12 hrs. The dark red solid residue left after concentrating the extract, was triturated with water to yield water insoluble colourless solid (2.1 g). The aqueous portion responded to Molish, Fehling and Seliwanoff tests positively and the sugar was identified as fructose by comparison with authentic sample (co-PC, *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water, v/v 4 : 1 : 5, Rf 0.19; *n*-butanol-benzene pyridine-water, v/v 5 : 1 : 3 : 3, Rf. 0.28, spray reagent aniline hydrogen phthalate).

The water insoluble residue was found to be a single substance by tlc (silica gel, water-acetic acid-conc. hydrochloric acid, v/v 1 : 3 : 3, Rf 0.81, NH₃/black spot) and was recrystallised from pyridine into yellow needles, m.p. above 360°. Found : C, 55.71%; H, 2.12%; Calcd. for C₁₄H₈O₈; C, 55.62%; H, 1.98%. It gave a green ferric reaction and negative response to Molish and Fehling tests. It was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate but soluble in sodium carbonate and sodium hydroxide solutions and was reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid, $\lambda_{\max}(\text{EtOH})$ 258 & 357 nm $\lambda_{\max}(\text{EtOH}-\text{NaOAc})$, 259 & 347 nm, $\nu_{\max}(\text{Nujol})$ 3350, 1700, 1610 cm⁻¹. It gave a tetracetate (NaOAc/Ac₂O) crystallizing from acetic anhydride as pale creamy crystals, m.p. 348-350°; lit⁸, m.p. 350-352°; Found : C, 56.24%; H, 3.22%; Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₄O₁₂; C, 56.00%; H, 3.0% $\lambda_{\max}(\text{EtOH})$

230, 280 (sh) & 340 nm, $\nu_{\max}(\text{Nujol}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ 1800, 1750, 1630; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) 2.2, (br.s, 12H, four x-O-CO-CH_3), 7.4 (s, 2H, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$ and $\text{C}_8\text{-H}$). The compound was finally established as 4,4', 5,5', 6,6'-hexahydroxy-diphenic acid dilactone by comparison (co-tlc, ir, uv and colour reactions) with the authentic sample of ellagic acid supplied by Fluka, Switzerland.

The powdered bark (150 g) was boiled with water (1.5l) and the tea coloured extract on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml) gave buff coloured precipitate (18.25 g). It was identified as tannin material by iron perchlorate, stiasny and boiling hydrochloric acid reactions. While boiling the bark with water, enough white particles that separated out, were identified as calcium oxalate by systematic analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. D. M. S. Amatya and T. U. authorities for research facilities and the scientific officers of R. D. R. L., Kathmandu for spectra.

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Synthesis of Some 1-Substituted-4-Phenyl-2(3H)-Imidazolethiones and Their Desulphurised Products

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Manuscript received 8 June 1979, revised 27 October 1980, accepted 10 March 1981

LITERATURE survey shows that 1-aryl substitution in the imidazole ring, in general, induces anaesthetic activity¹. A number of 2(3H)-imidazolethiones are used in clinical practice because of their

pronounced biological activity. 1-Methyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione is about hundred times more active than thiouracil². In view of these facts, we have synthesised fourteen new 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones. These have been further desulphurised to get 1,4-disubstituted imidazoles.

Experimental

Phenacyl bromide was condensed with different aromatic amines to get the corresponding phenacylamines (I). These in turn, were converted into 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones (II) by the method of Norrish and Mckee³. The thiones were desulphurised by Raney Nickel to get the 1-substituted-4-phenylimidazoles (III).

Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 377 infrared spectrophotometer in KBr phase and nujol mull. The compounds were analysed for carbon and hydrogen on Coleman analyser. All m.p.s were taken by capillary method and are uncorrected.

(A) *Synthesis of phenacylamines (I)*: The phenacylamines were synthesised by condensing phenacyl bromide with different aromatic amines by the known method⁴. The ir spectra of these showed the following characteristic bands.

$\text{Ir}_{\text{KBr}} \nu_{\max} (\text{cm}^{-1})$: 3380-3420 (NH), 1675-1685 (C=O), 1610-1600; 1570-1550; 1510-1500 (C=C); 1340-1350 (C-N); 1220 (C-CO-C).

The m.p. and elemental analysis of the new phenacylamines are given in Table 1.

(B) *Synthesis of 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones (II)*: A mixture of phenacylamine (1 mole), potassium thiocyanate (1 mole) in glacial acetic acid was heated under reflux for half an hour and the imidazolethiones were isolated by following the method of Norrish and Mckee³. Particulars of the compounds are listed in Table 2.

(C) *Synthesis of 1-substituted-4-phenylimidazoles (III)*: 1-Substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione (0.1 mole) was dissolved in absolute ethanol and about (0.4 mole) of freshly prepared Raney Nickel was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. The catalyst was filtered off and this solution evaporated on water bath to minimum. The cold mass was diluted with water to faint turbidity and set aside for 24 hrs, when a crystalline product separated. This was filtered and the mother liquid was allowed to evaporate at room temperature to get further crop of the product. These crops were collected and recrystallised to give pure product. The imidazoles obtained are listed in Table 3. Their structures were assigned on the basis of

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